

ECONOMIC IMPACT OF FLOOD ON RICE PRODUCTIVITY IN NIGER STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the economic impact of flood on the agricultural productivity of rural rice farmers in Niger State, Nigeria. The study adopted a quantitative, descriptive and cross-sectional survey research design. Using a cross-sectional survey design, primary data were collected from 392 rice farmers in flood-prone communities, representing a 91.4% response rate from the 429 questionnaires administered. Ordinary least square regression analysis shows that the explanatory account for only 1.18% of the variation in rice productivity ($R^2=0.0118$), indicating a statistically weak relationship. Despite this, flood remains a critical risk factor for rural farmers' livelihoods, with impacts likely shaped by unobserved factors like flood duration, soil drainage, and post-flood interventions. The study therefore recommends improved hydrological and drainage infrastructure, coordinated dam and water-release management, and policy incentives for the adoption of effective flood-adaptation strategies to enhance agricultural productivity under increasing flood exposure.

Keywords: *flood, rice productivity, rural farmers, Niger State, Nigeria.*

JEL Classification: Q12, Q54, O13, C21

1. INTRODUCTION

Flooding has emerged as one of the most pervasive environmental hazards undermining global economic stability, social welfare, and sustainable development, with its impacts intensifying in frequency and severity over recent decades. Globally, flood events occur with alarming regularity; for instance, Kim et al. (2023) reports an average of approximately 149 flood incidents annually worldwide, affecting diverse regions and agro-ecological zones. Although the magnitude, duration, and environmental consequences of floods vary across countries and communities, their economic repercussions are consistently severe, particularly in agriculture-dependent economies where livelihoods are highly climate-sensitive.

Flood-related losses typically manifest through human and livestock mortality, destruction of cropland and vegetation, damage to housing and infrastructure, and depletion of productive assets, cumulatively translating into substantial welfare and output losses. Empirical evidence suggests that such shocks disproportionately affect developing economies, where adaptive capacity and infrastructural resilience remain weak. Nigeria exemplifies this vulnerability, having experienced recurrent and increasingly destructive flood events that threaten national development objectives, especially in agriculture and food security.

Historically, flood disasters have been recorded across multiple Nigerian states, including Oyo (1985, 1987, 1990, 2011), Osun (1992, 1996, 2002, 2010, 2012, 2022, 2024), Yobe (2000, 2012, 2015, 2022, 2024), Ondo (1996–2006), and Niger State (1980, 2012, 2015, 2022, 2024), alongside repeated episodes in coastal and riverine states such as Rivers, Cross River, Benue,

and along the Niger waterways (Jonathan et al., 2020). These persistent occurrences have led scholars to characterize flooding as a macroeconomic development challenge of continental relevance (Amadi & Aleru, 2019).

The National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) reports that over 4 million people have been affected by floods across 34 states and 211 local government areas, with more than 300 lives lost and over 2,854 injured (NEMA, 2026a). The floods have also resulted in the displacement of over 729,000 people, with many living in temporary shelters. In terms of damage, the floods have destroyed or damaged over 200,000 houses and 440,000 hectares of farmland, leading to significant economic losses estimated at \$6.68 billion (₦4.2 trillion) (NEMA, 2026b). Some of the worst-affected states include Adamawa, Taraba, Benue, Niger, Nasarawa, Kebbi, Kogi, Edo, Delta, Anambra, Cross River, Rivers, and Bayelsa (NEMA, 2026a).

Despite extensive documentation of flood causes and humanitarian impacts, empirical evidence on the specific economic effects of flooding on rural farmers' productivity remains limited, especially at the micro level. This gap is critical, given that recurrent flood shocks pose a sustained threat to food security, income stability, and sustainable agricultural development. Advancing micro-econometric evidence on flood, and productivity linkages are essential for designing targeted adaptation and mitigation policies. Consequently, this study investigates the economic effects of flooding on rural farmers' productivity, with particular emphasis on Niger State, Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

2.1.1 Integrated Flood Management (IFM) Theory

The Integrated Flood Management (IFM) Theory was developed under the Associated Programme on Flood Management (APFM), a joint initiative of the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), and formally articulated in 2006. The theory emerged as a response to the limitations of traditional flood control approaches that focused primarily on structural measures such as dams, embankments, and levees, often neglecting social, economic, and environmental dimensions of flood risk (APFM, 2006; WMO, 2011).

Integrated Flood Management is defined as a holistic approach to flood risk management that seeks to balance flood risk reduction with sustainable development by integrating land and water management, environmental conservation, and socio-economic planning (APFM, 2006). The core assumption of IFM is that floods are natural phenomena that cannot be completely prevented; rather, they must be managed in ways that minimize economic losses, protect livelihoods, and enhance ecosystem services while maximizing the beneficial aspects of flood where possible (WMO, 2011; Koevoet et al., 2018).

2.1.2 Production Theory under Environmental Risk

Production theory provides the fundamental economic framework for analysing how inputs are transformed into outputs within an agricultural production system. Classical production theory, rooted in the works of economists and later refined by neoclassical economists, conceptualizes output as a function of key inputs including land, labour, capital, and technology, assuming stable production conditions and predictable input-output relationships.

However, agricultural production, particularly in developing economies, rarely operates under conditions of certainty. Instead, it is highly exposed to environmental risk and uncertainty, arising from climatic variability, natural disasters, and ecological shocks. Production theory under environmental risk extends the traditional framework by explicitly incorporating the role of stochastic and exogenous shocks--such as flood--into the production process.

Under this framework, flood is treated as a negative environmental shock that affects agricultural output through multiple channels. First, flood can cause direct physical damage to crops, leading to partial or total yield loss. Second, it can reduce input productivity by washing away fertilizers, damaging seedlings, eroding fertile topsoil, and disrupting labour utilization. Third, flood can destroy farm infrastructure such as irrigation facilities, storage structures, and access roads, thereby increasing production costs and reducing technical efficiency (Ndatsu, 2019). As a result, the production function becomes conditional not only on conventional inputs but also on environmental conditions.

In flood-prone environments, productivity is therefore best understood as a function of both input use and exposure to environmental shocks. This theoretical insight provides a strong justification for modelling rice output as a function of socio-economic characteristics, farm inputs, and flood-related variables, as adopted in this study. Specifically, the use of the Cobb-Douglas production function allows for the estimation of output elasticities while accommodating the inclusion of flood as an exogenous factor that shifts the production frontier downward. When flood occurs, farmers are unable to attain maximum output even with optimal input combinations, resulting in reduced productivity for a given level of inputs.

2.1.3 Wellbeing Theory (Objective Dimension)

Wellbeing theory provides an important conceptual framework for analyzing the broader economic and livelihood consequences of environmental shocks such as flood. While wellbeing is a multidimensional concept encompassing subjective, psychological, and emotional aspects of life, this study adopts the objective dimension of wellbeing, which emphasizes measurable and observable indicators of welfare. This approach is particularly appropriate for rural agrarian studies where welfare is closely linked to productive capacity, income stability, and access to basic necessities (Sen, 1985).

The objective wellbeing perspective is rooted in Amartya Sen's capability approach, which argues that wellbeing should be assessed based on individuals' ability to achieve valuable functioning--such as being adequately nourished, maintaining a stable livelihood, and having the means to sustain productive activities--rather than solely on subjective happiness or utility (Sen, 1999). In agricultural economies, this functioning is largely determined by farm productivity and income, making agricultural output a central indicator of objective wellbeing.

2.2 Empirical Review

Empirical evidence across sub-Saharan Africa consistently demonstrates that flooding exerts significant adverse effect on agricultural productivity, income distribution, and rural livelihoods. Using primary household data from Kwara State, Nigeria, Shehu (2014) applied descriptive statistics, partial budget analysis, and t-tests to evaluate flood impacts on farm profitability. The results revealed a statistically significant widening of the vulnerability gap between wealthier and poorer households, indicating that flood shocks disproportionately burden low-income farmers.

Similarly, Osasogie & Alabi (2015) employed descriptive statistics alongside Lorenz curve and Gini coefficient analyses to examine income distribution effects of flooding among farmers in Edo State, Nigeria. Their findings showed a post-flood decline in average farm income and a measurable increase in income inequality (higher Gini coefficient), suggesting that flood exposure exacerbates structural inequality among rural households.

Beyond Nigeria, Kim, et al. (2023) analyzed flood impacts on farmers' livelihoods in the semi-arid zone of Benin Republic using the Rubin causal model, logistic regression, and instrumental variable techniques. The study reported a negative and statistically significant effect of flooding on expected farm income ($p < 0.05$), providing robust causal evidence that flood exposure directly undermines livelihood sustainability. Similarly, according to Rupngam & Messiga

(2024), Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) data shows that between 2008 and 2018, USD 21 billion was lost in global agriculture due to floods, with impacts including oxygen depletion in soil and altered nutrient dynamics.

At the household level, Apuyor, Mohammad, and Ojo (2021) documented the socio-economic characteristics of rice farmers in flood-prone areas of Niger State, Nigeria. Their descriptive analysis showed that recurrent flooding negatively affects farmers' social status, asset accumulation, and welfare, reinforcing the multidimensional nature of flood vulnerability beyond yield losses alone.

Also, Oladapo (2021) analysed flooding incidence and coping strategies among rice farmers in Edu and Patigi Local Government Areas of Kwara State using descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, and regression analysis. The study found significant relationships between flood impact and socio-economic variables such as marital status, farm size, and household size, while also confirming that flooding leads to crop loss, yield reduction, and income decline despite the adoption of mitigation strategies.

Similarly, the findings of Soulibouth, Hwang & Shin (2021) indicated that floods cause severe damage to crops, lower agricultural productivity, and lead to reduced income and increased poverty among farmers.

Recent evidence by Nwagwu et al. (2024) combined descriptive statistics with regression analysis to assess flood effects on small-scale rice farmers in south-eastern Nigeria. The results indicated a statistically significant reduction in rice yield and farm revenue following flood events. While farmers adopted control measures, such as sandbag barriers, drainage construction, and water gates, these strategies were largely reactive and insufficient to fully offset flood-induced losses.

Collectively, the literature provides strong empirical support, using both descriptive and econometric techniques, that flooding significantly reduces farm productivity, income, and livelihood security across African rice-based systems. However, most studies emphasize short-term impacts and descriptive outcomes, with limited integration of real economic effects on productivity within a unified econometric framework. This gap motivates the present study's approach, which explicitly assesses how flood affect rural farmers productivity on economic scaling using robust econometric modelling.

3. METHODOLOGY

This investigation is majorly a quantitative study, employing primary data and standard econometric techniques for estimation. Basically data were collected using questionnaire and techniques of estimation involving Ordinary Least Square (OLS) to assess the economic impacts of flood on rural rice farmer's productivity in Niger state. Other relevant items in the methodological framework are explained in this section beginning with the study design, study area, population and sample size, sampling techniques, method of data collection and model of analyses.

3.1 Theoretical Framework

The Integrated Flood Management (IFM) theory provides the theoretical underpinning for the econometric framework adopted in this study. Developed under the Associated Programme on Flood Management (APFM) by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), IFM reconceptualizes flooding as an inevitable natural process whose economic effects are determined by levels of exposure, vulnerability, and adaptive capacity rather than hydrological factors alone. This perspective directly informs the empirical modelling strategy for this study.

Consistent with IFM, the study employs an Ordinary Least Square (OLS) technique to estimate the probability of achieving higher agricultural productivity under flood exposure. The dependent variable captures farmers' productivity status, while the explanatory variables

reflect IFM's multidimensional risk framework, incorporating flood characteristics alongside socio-economic and institutional factors such as land size, education, and credit access. This integrated specification acknowledges that flood impacts on productivity are mediated by management systems and local conditions (Koevoet et al., 2018). This helps to understand the dynamics of flood and its economic effect on farmer's productivity at the local level. The estimation of marginal effects enables direct interpretation of how flood exposure influence productivity outcomes, thereby translating IFM's conceptual claims into measurable economic effects. From an analytical standpoint, modest pseudo- R^2 values are consistent with IFM theory, which recognizes the influence of unobserved socio-economic and environmental factors. In the study view, this reinforces the suitability of an IFM-guided econometric approach for evaluating flood-induced productivity effects and deriving policy-relevant insights for integrated flood-risk management in rural agricultural systems.

3.2 Research Design

The study adopts a cross-sectional survey design, consistent with similar empirical studies in agricultural and environmental economics such as; Aboaba (2020), Muhammed et al. (2023). This design enables the collection of farm-level data from rice farmers at a single point in time, allowing for the assessment of the economic effects of flooding within one production season. This approach is particularly appropriate in flood-impact studies, where seasonal shocks can be clearly isolated and linked to observable economic outcomes.

3.3 Study Area

The study was conducted in Niger State, located between latitudes $8^{\circ}20'N$ and $11^{\circ}30'N$ and longitudes $3^{\circ}30'E$ and $7^{\circ}20'E$. The state shares boundaries with Kaduna, Kwara, Kogi, Kebbi States, and the Federal Capital Territory, positioning it as a critical agricultural corridor linking northern and southern markets. Niger state is endowed with extensive fertile alluvial plains along the River Niger, River Kaduna, and Gurara tributaries, which support large-scale and smallholder rice farming systems. Climatically, Niger State experiences distinct wet and dry seasons, with mean annual rainfall ranging from 1,200 mm to 1,600 mm, levels considered optimal for rain-fed lowland and irrigated rice production. These conditions, combined with relatively flat topography, have positioned Niger State as one of Nigeria's leading rice-producing areas. Figure 1 shows the map of the state and its local governments.

As observed in Figure 1, Niger State has twenty-one (21) Local Government Areas (LGAs), which include; Chanchaga, Magama, Rijau, Lapai, Agaie, Mokwa, Rafi, Bida, Tafa, Gurara, Kontagora, Lavun, Gbako, Edati, Paikoro, Wushishi, Bosso, Munya, Mashegu, Shiroro, and Agwara. Each of these LGAs contributes to agricultural output at varying scales, depending on ecological conditions, access to water bodies, and intensity of farming activities. The spatial distribution of LGAs across floodplains and river basins makes the state particularly suitable for examining flood-related agricultural outcomes.

Rice production is a dominant activity across many LGAs, especially those located along major river systems and floodplains. The Niger State Agricultural and Mechanization Development Authority (NAMDA, 2024) estimates that approximately 18,450 rural rice farmers operate within flood-prone areas of the state. These farmers are largely smallholders practicing rain-fed agriculture and are therefore highly vulnerable to climatic shocks, particularly seasonal flooding.

3.4 Population and Sample Size

The target population comprises all rural rice farmers cultivating within flood-prone areas of Niger State. These farmers have direct exposure to flood events and are therefore well positioned to provide first-hand information on production losses, income effects, and coping strategies. Using Yamane's (1967) sample size determination formula at a 5% level of precision, a sample size of approximately 390 respondents was derived, ensuring statistical representativeness while maintaining feasibility for field data collection. The selected

population and sample size are adequate for drawing valid inferences and for informing agricultural and climate-related policy interventions aimed at mitigating flood risks among smallholder farmers.

3.5 Sampling Technique

A multi-stage sampling technique was adopted to ensure fair representation of rice farmers across the flood-prone LGAs. The first stage involved the purposive selection of six flood-affected LGAs based on NEMA and NIMET flood records. The second stage involved random selection of communities within these LGAs that experienced significant flood in the last two years. The third stage involved random selection of individual rice farmers using lists provided by the Niger State Agricultural Development Project (NADP). Studies have employed similar multi-stage sampling techniques to assess the impact of flooding on rice farmers.

3.6 Method of Data Collection

The study relied on primary data. Primary data were collected through a well-structured questionnaire administered by trained enumerators fluent in local languages. The questionnaire was divided into sections covering farmers' socio-economic characteristics, input use, and rice output and flood experience. Each question was designed to capture easily observable or recallable information from farmers.

3.7 Reliability and Validity of Data Collection Instrument

3.7.1 Reliability of data collection instrument

The reliability of the primary data collected in this study was assessed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient and a pilot test. Cronbach's alpha was calculated to evaluate the internal consistency of the questionnaire. The questionnaire was pretested among 20 rice farmers in Shiroro LGA to ensure clarity and consistency, yielding a reliability coefficient (Cronbach's Alpha) of 0.82, which confirms internal validity.

3.7.2 Validity of Data Collection Instrument

The validity of the primary data collected in this study was assessed using content validity and construct validity. To ensure content validity, the questionnaire was reviewed by experts in the field to ensure that it adequately measures the research variables and that it reflects the research objectives. To ensure construct validity, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted to evaluate the construct validity of the questionnaire.

3.8 Method Data Analysis

Primary data collected from rural rice farmers in Niger state were used in the study. The raw data was sorted, coded and inputted for analysis. The descriptive analysis provided an overview of the sample characteristics, flood experiences, and adaptation strategies, which helped to identify patterns and trends in the data. The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) Model was employed to assess the impact of flood on productivity. Stata version 17 was used to conduct the data analysis.

3.9 Model specification

In order to quantify the impact of flood on rural rice farmers' productivity, an ordinary least squares (OLS) regression model was used, adapted from similarly specified models by Okorogwe, et al (2025) and Okoroigwe, et al. (2025), and is specified below:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 F + \beta_2 (FXD) + \sum Y_i X_i + \varepsilon$$
 used in previous

Where:

Y_i is rice yield (e.g., tons/ha),

F is flood experience (dummy variable),

D is duration,

$F X D$ represents damage intensity,

X_i is a vector of control variables such as land size, education, and credit access; and

ε is error term

3.10 Methodological Limitations: The study acknowledge potential limitations, including unobserved factors (e.g., soil fertility, infrastructure access) that may influence productivity. Future research could employ more robust techniques (e.g., instrumental variables, fixed effects) to address these concerns and strengthen causal inference.

4. DATA PRESENTATION

4.1 Response Rate

Table 1: Response Rate of the Survey

Description	Number
Original sample size	390
Additional 10% buffer	39
Total questionnaires administered	429
Correctly completed and returned	392
Questionnaires used for analysis	392

Source: Authors' computation from Stata Output (2026)

This section presents the response rate of the questionnaire administered for the study. The target sample size for the study was 390 respondents, which was determined to be adequate for statistical analysis based on the study population. In line with standard survey research practice, an additional 10 percent of the original sample size was added to account for potential non-response, incomplete questionnaires, and data attrition, thereby enhancing the robustness and reliability of the dataset.

4.2 OLS Regression Results, Interpretations and Discussion of Findings

To assess the economic effect of flood on rice productivity, an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression model was estimated using robust standard errors. The dependent variable was Yield (measured in kilograms per hectare), while the explanatory variables included Flood Exposure (FloodExp), Flood Duration (FloodDur), Education (Edu), Extension Visit (ExtVisit), and Credit Access (Credit). The OLS result are displayed in Table 2.

Table 2: OLS Regression Results for the Economic Effect of Flood

Yield	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
FloodExp	8.992	110.038	0.08	.935	-207.356	225.34	
FloodDur	-5.83	7.032	-0.83	.408	-19.656	7.996	
Edu	10.988	9.147	1.20	.23	-6.995	28.971	
ExtVisit	6.011	26.621	0.23	.821	-46.33	58.353	
Credit	130.674	87.641	1.49	.137	-41.64	302.988	
Constant	2389.985	180.43	13.25	0	2035.238	2744.733	***
Mean dependent var	2501.365		SD dependent var		852.913		
R-squared	0.012		Number of obs		392		
F-test	0.965		Prob > F		0.439		
Akaike crit. (AIC)	6409.737		Bayesian crit. (BIC)		6433.565		

*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1

Source: Authors' computation from Stata Output (2026)

The results in Table 2 show that the independent variables jointly explain about 1.18% of the total variation in rice yield ($R^2 = 0.0118$), suggesting that flood and related socio-economic factors contribute only marginally to yield variation. The F-statistic (0.97; $p = 0.4388$) indicates the overall model is not statistically significant at the 5% level. This modest explanatory power reflects the complex nature of flood impacts, which are influenced by numerous unobserved environmental and infrastructural factors such as soil drainage, flood timing, and recovery interventions. This is supported by the study of Alehile, et al. (2022), which established the existence of long-run relationship and also found that in the short run, lag of climate variations such as increase in rainfall index has a positive and statistically significant impact on crop output

The coefficient for Flood Exposure (FloodExp) is statistically insignificant ($\beta = 8.99$, $p = 0.935$), indicating no reliable impact on rice yield. Flood Duration (FloodDur) has a negative but insignificant coefficient ($\beta = -5.83$, $p = 0.408$), aligning with expectations of waterlogging effects.

Education (Edu) and Extension Visit (ExtVisit) show positive but insignificant coefficients, suggesting potential benefits in knowledge and adaptation practices. This is conforms with the findings of Oduntan & Obisesan (2022), study which showed that crop diversification was the most adopted climate smart agricultural practice by the farmers in Nigeria and adoption of Climate Smart Agricultural practices is still very low among the respondents. Also, the study obtains support from Dzarma, et al. (2024), which suggests that stakeholders should focus primarily on improving labour and seed inputs to maximize efficiency in rice production

Credit Access (Credit) has a positive but insignificant relationship with yield, indicating potential financial resilience. This is supported by the findings of Onyenekwe, et al. (2025), which discovered that factors influencing food security and poverty included marital status, household size, occupation, income, and farm size, and key challenges to urban agriculture were limited space, lack of credit access, and climate change. In the same vein, findings from Abdul, et al. (2022) revealed that agriculture financing has a positive impact on food security in Nigeria, with the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund and bank credit to the agricultural sector having positive coefficients in the long-run and in the short-run.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

This study examined the economic effect of flood on rural rice farmers' productivity in Niger State, Nigeria. The OLS regression results showed no significant effect of flood on rice yield, highlighting the complexity of flood impacts. The model's low explanatory power and insignificant coefficients suggest potential omitted variables.

Policy interventions promoting human capital development and rural financial inclusion can enhance farmers' resilience. Future research could explore additional factors (e.g., soil fertility, infrastructure access) and employ more robust econometric techniques to address endogeneity.

5.2 Recommendations

- i. Government and development agencies should prioritize the provision of subsidized fertilizers and promote the formation and strengthening of farmer cooperatives. Cooperatives should be supported with training, input pooling, and market linkage programs to improve resource access and collective bargaining power.
- ii. Extension services should be revitalized to provide tailored advice on flood-resilient farming practices. Financial instruments such as crop insurance and

emergency credit should be made accessible to farmers to cushion post-flood recovery and reduce productivity shocks.

- iii. Adaptation support programs should move beyond generic approaches and integrate indigenous knowledge with scientific insights. Participatory extension models, farmer field schools, and community-based adaptation planning should be encouraged to foster locally relevant and sustainable coping strategies.

5.3 Suggestion for Further Study

Future research could employ more robust techniques (e.g., instrumental variables, fixed effects) to address these concerns of unobserved factors (e.g., soil fertility, infrastructure access) that may influence productivity. And strengthen causal inference.

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